

SOME CONSIDERATIONS FOR LEARNING AND MASTERING MEDICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract: This article discusses the acquisition of medical terms and their use in the Latin language and medical terminology class. The meaning of medical terms, Latin and Greek clinical and pharmaceutical terms are widely used in modern medicine.

Key words: term element, carcinoma, criterion, ancient Greek terms, epidemic, dysfunction, anuria.

INTRODUCTION

The object of study in the course of medical Latin are words and phrases that denote special concepts of medical science. Such words and phrases are called terms, and their combination forms medical terminology - the professional language of medical workers. The medical specialist must competently use the constantly updated professional language and understand the laws that determine the emergence of terms.

Doctors of any country use a mass of international, generally accepted terms that have arisen on the basis of ancient Greek and Latin. These terms are universal and understandable to professionals regardless of their nationality. Such terms-internationalisms constitute the main fund of medical science. The most ancient period includes such terms as epidemic (*epidemia*), bronchus (*bronchus*), herpes (*herpes*), carcinoma (*carcinoma*), emphysema (*emphysema*)

The terminologies of individual sciences consist of tens and hundreds of thousands of terms. The starting point in terminology is the position that the purpose of a term is to briefly, accurately and unambiguously express a scientific concept. For this, the term must have the following criteria: adequacy, unambiguity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In real-life terminology, not all terms meet these requirements. Therefore, specialists from various sciences, including medicine, pay great attention to streamlining and standardizing their professional language.

The terminological system of modern medicine consists of many subsystems, among which there are three leading ones: anatomical and histological terminology, pharmaceutical terminology and clinical terminology.

The names of functional disorders are usually formed using a combination of prefix and root term elements. Of the prefixed TEs, the prefix *dys-* is most often used in combination with the final root TE: *dyskinesia*, *ae f - dyskinesia*, a disorder of coordinated motor acts. A combination of the noun *dysfunctio*, *onis f - dysfunction* and the name of a specific organ is also used: *dysfunctio renum - kidney dysfunction*. The complete cessation or absence of some

function or physiological process is expressed using the prefix a - (an - before a vowel): *aphagia, ae f* - aphagia, complete inability to swallow; *anuria, ae f* - anuria, failure of urine to enter the bladder

The names of pathological processes and conditions are compiled using prefix, suffix and root TEs, and are also expressed in Latin noun terms. At the same time, a definition is often added to nouns that characterizes the peculiarity of this pathological process (*acute, chronic, complete, partial, etc.*).

Almost all prefixes are used as prefix TEs, but Greek prefixes are much more common than Latin ones. Their meaning in clinical terms usually coincides with the meaning in anatomical terms.

However, it is often difficult to determine the meaning of the Greek prefix in many terms, since, firstly, the root morphemes of such terms without prefixes are not used in medical terminology, and secondly, the Greek prefixes themselves have a lot of meanings. Therefore, in such cases, it is necessary to assimilate the term without highlighting the prefix in it and without conducting a morphological analysis of the word, for example: *diabetes, ae m* - *diabetes*, the name of a group of diseases of an endocrine nature, characterized by excessive excretion of urine from the body.

The terms "pharmaceutics" and "pharmacy" are of ancient Greek origin and go back to the word *pharmakon* medicine. Subsequently, through Latin, these two terms entered all the languages of Europe. Medicine traditionally uses Latin and Latinized Greek words in the names of raw materials for the production of medicines, in the names of medicines and in the recipe.

The list of Latin names of dosage forms and drugs is the International Pharmaceutical Nomenclature. From time to time, as some drugs or dosage forms become obsolete and other drugs or dosage forms appear, the list of pharmaceutical terms is reviewed and updated.

Uppercase and lowercase letters in dictionary form and as part of a pharmaceutical term are very important. Capital letters are written both in dictionary form and as part of the term:

1. Names of medicinal plants: *Chamomilla, ae f* - *chamomile*; *Flores Chamomillae* - *chamomile* flowers; *Frangula, ae f* - *buckthorn*; *Decoctum corticis Frangulae* - *decoction* of buckthorn bark.

2. Names of chemical elements and cations: *Ferrum, i n* - *iron*; *Sirupus Aloës cum Ferro* - *aloe* syrup with iron; *Strychninum, i n* - *strychnine*; *Solutio Strychnini nitratis* is a solution of strychnine nitrate.

3. Names of drugs: *Prednisolonum, i n* - *prednisolone*; *Tabulettae Prednisoloni* - *prednisolone* tablets; *Leonurus, i m* - *motherwort*; *Tinctura Leonuri* is motherwort tincture.

4. Words equivalent to medicines: *Amylum, i n* - *starch*; *Gelatina, ae f*—*gelatin(a)*; *Gelatosa, ae f*—*gelatosis*; *Propolisum, i n* - *propolis*; *Saccharum, i n* - *sugar*.

Clinical terminology (from the Greek *klinike* (techne) - care for bedridden patients) is the most extensive section of medical terminology. Here are the names of various diseases and abnormalities, methods of investigation and treatment, clinical specialties and specialists. All of these names are mostly nouns. Such nouns can be single-root words (*asthma, atis n* - *asthma*; *hernia, ae f* - *hernia*). However, in most cases they are complex in composition and consist mainly of Greek word-forming elements, or term elements (TE): *hyperaesthesia* - hypersensitivity.

There are affixal and root TEs. Affixal TEs are prefixes and suffixes. For example, the prefix *hypo* - forms terms with the meaning "below the norm": *hypothermia* - *hypothermia*, lowering the temperature, *hypothermia*; *hypothyreosis* - *hypothyroidism*, decreased thyroid function; *hypoxia* - *hypoxia*, a decrease in the level of oxygen in the tissues. The suffix *-oma* usually means "tumor": *lipoma*, a tumor of adipose tissue; *odontoma* - *odontoma*, a tumor of dental tissue. Root TEs are the roots or stems of Greek and sometimes Latin nouns, adjectives or pronouns. It is customary to divide root FCs into initial and final ones. Initial TEs are connected with suffixes or final TEs. For example, TE *angi* - with the meaning of "vessel" can be combined with suffixes *-itis* or *-oma* in terms of *angioma* (*angioma*, tumor from the tissue of blood vessels) and *angiitis* (*angiitis*, inflammation of the walls of blood vessels). At the same time, this TE can be combined with root end TEs: *angiosclerosis* (*angiosclerosis*, hardening of the walls of blood vessels), *angiospasmus* (*angiospasm*, spasm of blood vessels).

The initial TE is usually attached to another, including the final TE, with the help of a connecting vowel *-o-*: *bronchospasmus* - *bronchospasm*, narrowing of the bronchi. If the TE, to which the initial TE is attached, begins with a vowel, then the connective *-o-*, as a rule, is omitted: *nephrectomy* - *nephrectomy*, the operation to remove the kidney. However, sometimes this rule is not respected and the connective *-o-* is preserved: *acroaesthesia* - hypersensitivity distal parts of the body.

Root TEs can often act as both initial and final terminological elements, for example: *nos-* and *-nosis* (illness, illness), cf.: *nosologia*, *ae f* - *nosology*, the doctrine of the forms of diseases and their classification; *zoonosis*, *is f* - *zoonosis*, infectious diseases transmitted from animals to humans. In such cases, students are required to know both of these options and give them in an oral or written response: illness, disease - *nos-*, *-nosis*.

Root TEs can connect with each other, forming multicomponent structures: *chole* (bile) + *cyst* (bladder) - > *cholecyst* - (gall bladder): *cholecystographia* - *cholecystography* - radiography of the gallbladder.

Root TEs can sometimes have multiple meanings. So, the initial TE *kerat* - can have 2 meanings: 1) the cornea of the eye; 2) the stratum corneum of the epidermis of the skin, cf.: *keratitis* - *keratitis*, inflammation of the cornea of the eye; *keratosis* - *keratosis*, the general name of skin diseases characterized by thickening of the stratum corneum of the epidermis.

The names of sciences, specialties and sections of medicine are most often formed with the help of the final TE - *logia*: *ophthalmologia*, *ae f* - *ophthalmology*. On the basis of TE - *logia*, adjectives are formed with the final element *-logicus*, *a*, *um* (the Russian equivalent is *logical*), which indicates belonging to some group of sciences, sections of clinical medicine, methods of research or treatment: *bacteriologicus*, *a*, *um* - *bacteriological* pertaining to bacteriology.

Some names of sections of clinical medicine are formed with the help of the final TE - *iatria*: *geriatria*, *ae f* - *geriatrics*, a section of clinical medicine dedicated to diseases of the senile age and methods of their treatment.

The names of some sections of clinical medicine are descriptive:

morbi interni - *internal diseases*;

morbi infectiosi - *infectious diseases*.

The names of some clinicians are formed with the help of TE - *pathologus* and *-iater*, and such terms always correlate with the names of the corresponding sections of clinical medicine: *neuropathologia*, *ae f* - *neuropathologus*, *i m* - *neuropathologist*, specialist in diseases

of the peripheral nervous system. The Latin names of specialists, which in English equivalents have a final element - ist, are masculine nouns of the I declension with a final element - ista: infectious disease specialist - infectionista, ae m - specialist in infectious diseases.

CONCLUSION

The names of specialists who have a final element in Russian equivalents - pat, are nouns of the II declension with a final element - *pathus: naturopath - naturopathus, i m - a doctor who uses only natural remedies (living and inanimate nature) for treatment.*

Today, Latin is not only the memory of the philosophers, speakers, poets of Ancient Rome, but also an indispensable attribute of the modern world. Latin is firmly rooted in scientific terminology in many fields of knowledge, especially in medicine, biology and jurisprudence. Therefore, they even single out medical, biological and legal Latin separately. In medicine, almost all medical terms are of Latin-Greek origin.

References:

1. Israilova M. N., Yuldasheva D. Y. PECULIARITIES OF TEACHING LATIN LANGUAGE AT MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES //Eastern European Scientific Journal. – 2021. – №. 2.
2. Israilova M. N. New Pedagogical Technologies of Studying Latin in Medical Schools //Eastern European Scientific Journal. – 2017. – №. 1.
3. Israilova M. N., Yuldasheva D. Y., Sayfullaeva L. S. Innovative Technologies of Teaching //American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 12. – C. 23-26.
4. Israilova M. N. THE ROLE OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENCE OF PEDAGOGY //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 1288-1291.
5. Israilova M. N., Eshquvatova G. B., Duldulova N. A. TIBBIYOT OLIY O'QUV YURLARIDA MUAMMOLI TA'LIM //Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art. – 2023. – C. 22-23.
6. ISRAILOVA M. N. LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY FARMATSEVTIK TERMINOLOGIYA ASOSLARI //Tibbiyot oliygohi talabalari uchun o 'quv qo 'llanma T-2016.
7. Israilova M. N., Muxammadjon I. XORIJIY TILLARNI O 'QITISHDA INTERNETDAN FOYDALANISHNING AFZALLIKLARI //Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art. – 2023. – C. 24-26.
8. Israilova M. N. ZAMONAVIY DARS XXI ASRNING ASOSIY KOMPONENTI SIFATIDA //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 13. – C. 109-110.
9. Israilova M. N. et al. Lotin Tilining Bugungi Zamon Tibbiyotidagi Ahamiyati //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2023. – T. 33. – C. 9-11.
10. Israilova M. N., Sayfullayeva L. S. XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARINING O'RNI //PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 17. – C. 180-181.